

HISTORICAL SCIENCES

ON THE ISSUE OF RECOGNITION OF ANCIENT AUTOCEPHALY AND THE PATRIARCHAL DIGNITY OF THE GEORGIAN CHURCH BY THE ECUMENICAL PATRIARCHATE

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Abstract

The article discusses the issue of recognition of ancient autocephaly and patriarchal dignity of the Georgian Church. The initiator of the process of recognition of ancient autocephaly and the patriarchal dignity of the Georgian Church was His Holiness Patriarch of Georgia Ilia II.

After many years of struggle, the final recognition of the autocephaly of the Georgian Orthodox Church occurred in 1990. On January 7, 1990, after a service in Zion, Metropolitan Chrysostomos, who visited Georgia, officially announced the decision of the Ecumenical Patriarchate to recognize the historical autocephaly of the Georgian Apostolic Church and the patriarchal title of its head.

Then Catholicos-Patriarch Ilia II spoke. In his sermon, he emphasized the fact that the Georgian Church has been autocephalous since ancient times and was headed by a Catholicos.

Keywords: Georgian Church, autocephaly, patriarchal dignity

The initiator of the process of recognizing ancient autocephaly and the patriarchal dignity of the Georgian Church was His Holiness Patriarch Ilia II. Metropolitan Anania Japaridze has held various positions in the Patriarchate since 1981 and the last position, which dates back to this time, this era, was the chairman of the economic and financial department, he personally saw His Holiness the Patriarch every day, his opinion, his thinking, his mind, on what he worked on what was the most important painful issue for him, and observed that the work and thought of the Patriarch every day and every moment was a confirmation of the autocephaly of the Patriarchate of the world. He tried to find and obtain documents, letters, Gujars, they were scattered throughout what was then Georgia, some of them were in the state archive, some in the Institute of Manuscripts, some in the Patriarchate. It was chaos in all spheres, and the Patriarch gathered, organized and gave it a face. The Metropolitan's duty was to deliver letters from abroad and their brief contents to the Patriarch, and he saw that when letters arrived from Constantinople, he wrote not the word Patriarch, but the word: Unetaresi Catholicos Elijah. II was used. . Since this was repeated very often, Metropolitan Anania turned to the Patriarch on this topic. It was this question that interested the patriarch; he tried with all his might to assign the title of patriarch to our first hierarch; he was worried that the first hierarch of the Universal Church of Georgia was not mentioned as a patriarch. The Patriarch answered his question like this:

“This is precisely the main issue, that Constantinople does not recognize the dignity of the Patriarch of the Georgian Church, and I am working precisely on this topic.”

After this, the Patriarch instructs Metropolitan Anania Japaridze to prepare the topic of autocephaly... He invents historical events of that time, notes:

„They loved our patriarch very much then, they loved him very much. For example, I remember very well, I was then the manager of the diocese, I led the Samtskhe-Javakheti diocese, which was a very large diocese. I was lucky and blessed the Safari Church there, which today is a monastery, and also blessed Vardzi. 200-300 years of Zarzma, where I founded a school and seminary. Our Patriarch, following Patriarch Nicholas VI of Alexandria and All Africa, visited Tbilisi, brought it as a guest to my diocese and brought it to the funeral. Safarah was not active at that time, and it was then that he said that it should be a cathedral, and not the small church that we had in Rabat. And by this I mean that I could see how much Nicholas VI loved him, saying:

- Yes, you are the patriarch, we will definitely meet in Constantinople.

The amazing authority and amazing personal abilities of our Patriarch, his love led to the fact that in 1990 our Church was granted autocephaly.

We have had autocephaly for centuries, we have always had it, constantly, and a miracle happened when at the beginning of the 19th century the autocephaly of our Church was abolished by the Russian Empire. What right did the Russian Empire have? As you know, in 1783 the Treaty of Georgievsk was signed between Russia and Georgia; it was a treaty of friendship, a friendly act. What did the Georgians demand? Georgians constantly asked the Russian Empire to help strengthen the army, give them weapons, and help them regain lost territories. And Russia promised that the Georgians would have their own independent state, promised that it would unite Georgia, return the lost

land and water, which today is called Saingilo, which was part of Char-Belakan, the nest of the Lekians. Russia promised to return this territory to Georgia, because it was our historical land and water, and most importantly, it promised to return Samtskhe-Saatabago, that is, Samtskhe-Javakheti, and this was a huge territory, starting with Erzurum, the northern part. modern Turkey. This is what is written in the agreement, it is written that Russia recognized the Bagrationi as the permanent holders of the royal throne of Georgia, it is also written that it will help with weapons and create a strong army, and who would not sign such an agreement?

We can say that the Russians entered Georgia with such an agreement and, of course, it was violated, they violated the terms of the agreement. We were promised the integrity of the state and the complete destruction of statehood.

We, the Georgian people, have always had our own state, it was and is a source of our pride. Although after the 11th century almost no people of the Caucasus had a state, we were the only ones. We even had states, that is, there were several Georgian states and they were all destroyed.

1. The Bagrationi were promised that they would be on the royal throne forever, and they canceled this, and then they approached the church, as you say, in 1811 they abolished the autocephaly of the Georgian Church, of course illegally, they had no right, because this decision could have been adopted only at the World Church Assembly, I repeat once again that the imperial court did not have the right to abolish the autocephaly of the Georgian Church.

In 1963, Catholicos-Patriarch Ilia II, who was still the creator bishop, at the Forum of Orthodox Churches on the island of Rhodes noted the disrespect for the Georgian Church, since they did not officially recognize the autocephaly of the Georgian Church. At the invitation of Catholicos-Patriarch Ilia II, on June 1-4, 1978, a delegation of the Ecumenical Patriarchate headed by Metropolitan Meliton of Chalcedon was in Tbilisi. The first serious negotiations on the recognition of autocephaly took place in the Patriarchate of Georgia. Georgian scientists were present at the meeting; Professors: M. Lortkipanidze, N. Lomouri, O. Japaridze, P. Zakaraya, Sh. Lom-Sadze, I. Sikharulidze, G. Mamulia, N. Asatiani, R. Siradze, A. Bogveradze, D. Gogoladze, T. Beradze, I. Lolashvili, B. Lominadze. On behalf of the Patriarch, Georgian scientists had to study the history of the Apostolic Church of Georgia, since it was necessary to resolve the issue of recognition of autocephaly.

On May 2-8, 1979, Catholicos-Patriarch Ilia II and his retinue were in Istanbul at the invitation of His Holiness Demetrius, Ecumenical Patriarch of Constantinople. At the meeting, His Holiness and Blessed Ilia II said: "When the Ecumenical Patriarchate of Constantinople sends us a letter or congratulations, the Catholicos-Patriarch of All Georgia, as he has been called since the 5th century, is incorrectly mentioned... The Georgian Church must legitimately take its place. When a violation of the place of belonging occurs, this affects the Georgian Apostolic Church and its authority

throughout the world... We want this issue to be resolved once and for all.

During this period, the visits of the heads of Orthodox churches to Georgia were of great importance. The main issue at the meetings with them was the recognition of autocephaly and the place of the Georgian Church in the diptych.

Regarding his place in the diptych, Catholicos-Patriarch Ilia II asked for written support, and his request was answered positively by: Patriarch of All Rus' Pimen (IX 29, 1982), Metropolitan of Prague and Czechoslovakia Dosifei (1982 16.VII), Patriarch Maxim of Bulgaria (16.V, 1982), Pope and Patriarch of Alexandria and All Africa Nicholas V (1982, 1.IX). The letter of the Jerusalem Patriarch Diodorus is noteworthy: "I would like to remind you that with the unanimity of the local Orthodox Churches, the martyred, but at the same time glorious Georgian Patriarchate must take its rightful place in the diptych of the Ecumenical Patriarchate of Constantinople."

The final recognition of the autocephaly of the Georgian Orthodox Church occurred in 1990 after many years of struggle. On January 7, 1990, after a service in Zion, Metropolitan Chrysostomos, who was on a visit to Georgia, officially announced the decision of the Ecumenical Patriarchate to recognize the historical autocephaly of the Apostolic Church of Georgia and the patriarchal title of its head. The next day, January 8, His Holiness and Blessed Ilia II read the final text. Instead of the words "I admit" and "I acknowledge," "I affirm" and "I declare" were written all over the place. In addition, according to one of the latest articles, the Georgian Church was supposed to receive chrism from the Church of Constantinople. The argument continued. The Greek Metropolitan corrected this with his own hands, but noted that the issue of Myron was beyond my competence and strength. Catholicos-Patriarch Ilia II strictly stated regarding myrrh: "According to historical documents available in Georgia, myrrh has been prepared since the 8th century. There are hypotheses that push this date back to an even earlier era... I do not doubt your words, but I must inform you that neither I, nor Demetrius I, nor any of us are immortal at all. I cannot leave a controversial issue for posterity. Who will forgive me if today with one signature I revoke the right received many centuries ago?~

Finally, it was agreed that if the Synod of the Church of Constantinople agrees to the option proposed by the Georgian Church, then Metropolitan Chizostom will send a telegram, and on March 4, an Orthodox holiday in Istanbul, the relevant documents will be solemnly presented. handed over to the head of the Georgian Church. On March 1, the delegation of the Georgian Church left Tbilisi for Moscow. After receiving visas, the delegation flew on March 3, first to Berlin and then to Istanbul. The delegation included: 1. Catholicos-Patriarch of All Georgia Ilia II, 2. Metropolitan of Tskhum-Abkhazia David (Chkadua), 3. Archbishop of Kutel-Gaenatsky Kalistrat (Margalishvili), 4. Rector of the Theological Faculty Protopresbyter George (Gamrekeli). Seminary and Academy, 5. Archdeacon of the Zion Cathedral Amiran Amiranashvili, 6. Greek translator of the Patriarchate Tamar Meskhi, 7.

Secretary of Foreign Affairs of the Patriarchate Boris Gagua.

On March 3, Patriarch of Constantinople His Holiness Demetrius I received the Georgian delegation at the Constantinople residence. The chapel took place, after which the secretary of the Holy.

The recognition of autocephaly of the Georgian Church was soon followed by a natural response from the state. According to the resolution of the Council of Ministers of the Georgian SSR dated April 12, 1990 No. 183: Article 2. Since the Georgian Orthodox Church is autocephalous, it is established that the accounting of the Orthodox Churches in Georgia, their property and funds is carried out independently by the Patriarchate of the Georgian Orthodox Church. According to Article 3, all religious buildings on the territory of Georgia, together with their real and movable property, were declared the property of the Georgian Church.

After the declaration of independence, the basis for a constitutional agreement between church and state was laid. In this regard, the Holy Synod of the Georgian Church determined: since in 1801 Sakartvelo illegally lost its state independence, and in 1811 - church independence... Today, when historical justice is being restored, the Apostolic Orthodox Church of Georgia believes that religious politics, implemented during the

period of annexation, and other actions cannot be considered legal, and reserves the right to declare the restoration of the situation (status quo) before the loss of independence within its canonical limits.

On October 14, 2002, at the Patriarchal Cathedral of Svetitkhovli in Mtskheta, a constitutional agreement was signed between the state of Georgia (President Eduard Shevardnadze) and the Apostolic Autocephalous Orthodox Church of Georgia (Catholic Patriarch Ilia II). The constitutional treaty recognizes the Georgian Orthodox Church as a legal entity of public law and defines the powers of the church in the spheres of culture, education, defense and justice. Orthodox churches, monasteries, land plots, church treasures in museums and warehouses are declared the property of the church.

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